

Surface Fuel Load and Fire Incidents Across various stages of Forest Stand in the Sub-Tropical Chir Pine Forest

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SUMMARY

Forest fires are uncontrolled events triggered by lightning, human activities, or volcanic eruptions. Although some fires benefit ecosystems by clearing dead vegetation and stimulating plant growth, frequent fires in Chir pine forests can severely damage different tree growth stages. This study investigated surface fuel loads and fire incidents at various growth stages in the subtropical Chir pine forest of Karakar, District Swat. Data on fire events from 2000 to 2022 were collected from relevant agencies to compare fire occurrences across young, middle-aged, and mature forest stands. Fuel loading and foliage retention were measured using randomly collected samples before burning. Fuel materials were categorized as needles or branches, and their depths were measured at three points before being taken to the lab to determine oven-dry weights. Statistical analysis showed that mature stands experienced more fire incidents due to greater surface fuel accumulation and dried needles, with fires peaking in May and July. Middle-aged stands recorded the most fires in 2019, while younger stands saw the highest incidents in 2009. Significant differences in fuel loads were observed between young and mature stages, influencing fire behavior and susceptibility. The study highlighted that fuel loads vary considerably across different stand stages, impacting wildfire risks, with mature stands showing unique fuel characteristics compared to younger ones. These findings emphasize the need for targeted forest management strategies, such as prescribed burns and fuel reduction, tailored to each stand stage. A comprehensive fire management plan considering surface fuel quantity and composition is essential to improve wildfire prevention and suppression in subtropical Chir pine forests.

Key words: Forest fire, fuel load, chir pine forest, tree stages

INTRODUCTION

Subtropical Chir pine (*Pinus roxburghii*) forests provide essential ecosystem services, including watershed protection and habitat for wildlife. However, they are highly vulnerable to human-induced fires, largely due to local resource dependence and prolonged dry conditions (Muhammad et al., 2024). These fires not only degrade air and water quality but also disrupt wildlife habitats and cause significant economic losses through property damage and firefighting expenses (Mather, 2003). Additionally, the frequency and intensity of wildfires are escalating due to climate change, which alters weather patterns and lengthens fire seasons (Luo et al., 2013). In Chir pine forests, sulfur-rich soil and extreme temperatures contribute to high fire susceptibility during certain months (Hashmi et al., 2014; Negi and Kumar, 2016). Effective fire management strategies, such as controlled burns, mechanical thinning,

and fuel moisture modeling, have shown promise in reducing fire severity and improving fire risk management (Burgan et al., 1998; Chuvieco et al., 2004; Stephens, 1998).

Forest fires significantly impact ecosystems by altering habitats, influencing species migration, and modifying soil composition, potentially leading to soil erosion and ecological imbalance (Kandya et al., 1998; Shvidenko and Goldammer, 2001). In Pakistan, forest degradation is exacerbated by frequent fires, particularly in Chir pine forests, where locals often ignite fires to clear pine needles, inadvertently increasing fire risks (Iqbal, 2003; Mahmud, 1998). Similar challenges are observed in Jammu and Kashmir, where frequent fires during hot, dry summers have degraded forest health, a situation worsened by climate change that extends fire seasons and intensifies droughts (Luo et al., 2013). Comprehensive fire management strategies are crucial for enhancing ecosystem resilience and promoting sustainable forest resource management. These include integrating prescribed burns, mechanical thinning, and controlled grazing to reduce surface fuel loads and fire severity (Stephens et al., 2009). Advanced methods, such as weather-based fire hazard indexes and detailed fuel categorization, are necessary for accurate fire risk assessments, though challenges persist due to the temporal and spatial variability of surface fuels (Keane, 2012). Additionally, adaptive fire management strategies are needed to address changing fire regimes influenced by global warming (Reinhardt et al., 2008; Swetnam, 1993). Given the significance of surface fuel management, this study aims to investigate the characteristics and dynamics of surface fuel wood across different growth stages of tree species in the subtropical Chir pine forests of the Karakar region, District Swat. The findings will contribute to the development of targeted fuel reduction strategies tailored to the unique ecological conditions of this region, ultimately supporting effective fire prevention and sustainable forest management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area description

Chir pine zone of Swat is situated in northern Pakistan within the Hindukush Mountain range. District Swat supports diverse vegetation, including scrub, temperate, alpine, and Chir pine species. Chir pine forests in this area are found at elevations between 800 m and 1700 m across the districts of Swat, (Ali et al., 2008). The study was conducted in Karakar region of Swat district (Figure 1).

Swat valley, situated in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan is a well-known and exceptionally beautiful location. It is bordered by Chitral district to the north, Indus Kohistan to the east, District Buner to the south, and district Dir to the west. The valley is mainly covered by forests, hills, mountains, lush vegetation, and agricultural land, contributing to its vast biodiversity, which is influenced by the diverse geographical and climatic conditions. Swat valley provides habitats for different forest types and wildlife species based on the varying climatic conditions. The valley is a famous destination for local, national, and international tourism, featuring numerous attractions such as kalam, Malam jabba, Marghuzar, Gabinjabba, Bahrain, Madyan, and Miandam. The distribution of forests in Swat is primarily determined by climate and altitude, with most regions lying in subtropical chirr pine

zone. But alpine and sub-alpine zone forests, as well as dry and moist temperate forests, are also found at higher elevations.

Figure 1: Map of Karakar valley, district Swat.

Study design

The study aimed to evaluate fire incidents in forest stands classified as young, pole, and mature. Data was recorded from 2000 to 2022. For this purpose, forest records were obtained from relevant agencies to compare fire incidents across the three stand types. The frequency of fire events was then compared among these stand categories.

Fuel loading and foliage retention were evaluated in each plot by collecting three randomly selected samples before burning in areas prone to forest fires. A total of 10 sites were sampled, but fires occurred in only four of these locations. Fuel material within a 30×30 cm sampling frame was removed to the mineral soil, categorized as needles or branches, and fuel depths were measured at three points using a ruler. Subsamples from each fuel component were weighed, stored in nylon bags, and taken to the lab to determine oven-dry weights, which were then used to calculate the total fuel loading for each plot. These samples were transported to the laboratory, where they were oven-dried at a constant temperature until a stable weight was achieved. The oven-dry weights were recorded and used to calculate the total fuel loading for each plot. This method provided a reliable estimate of the available fuel load, which is crucial for understanding fire behavior and developing effective fire management strategies.

Statistical analysis

To evaluate fire incidents in forest stands classified as young, pole, and mature, data was recorded from 2000 to 2022, and time series graph was then used to analyze the trends across these stand types. For comparison of fire incidents in various stages of stand, one way ANOVA was applied where the stages were taken as treatment at 0.05 probability in SPSS.

RESULTS

Time series analysis

The history of forest fire incidents was documented using data collected from the forest department for the period from 2000 to 2022. Although some data gaps exist due to the period of Talibanization in the Swat region, the available records (Figure 2) indicate that mature stands experienced more fire incidents compared to middle-aged and young stands.

Figure 2: Time series analysis of fire incidents in various stages of forest crop.

Comparison of fire incidents in various stages of stand

Similarly, statistical analysis revealed that mature stands experienced more fire incidents, likely due to greater surface fuel and dried needles, with fires occurring predominantly in the driest months, May and July (Figure 3). Notably, middle-aged stands recorded more fires in 2019, while younger stands had the highest fire incidents in 2009.

Similarly, The analysis of mean differences between the young, middle, and mature stages revealed significant differences between the young and middle stages ($p = 0.020$), young and mature stages ($p = 0.007$), and mature and young stages ($p = 0.007$). The study also found that fuel loads vary significantly across forest stand stages, influencing fire susceptibility, with mature stands showing distinct fuel characteristics compared to middle and young stands (Table 1). Therefore, while the Young and mature groups differ significantly, the middle and mature groups do not.

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Figure 3: number of fire incidents in various stage crop.

Table 1: Significant value for various stages of crops at 95% confidence interval

Groups		Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Young	Middle	0.020	-47.6470	-4.4610
	Mature	0.007	-52.2870	-9.1010
Middle	Young	0.020	4.4610	47.6470
	Mature	0.663	-26.2330	16.9530
Mature	Young	0.007	9.1010	52.2870
	Middle	0.663	-16.9530	26.2330

DISCUSSION

The study aimed to achieve two main objectives: first, to analyze the history of forest fires across different plantation stages, and second, to investigate the relationship between fuel load and fire incidents in the study area. The findings revealed significant variations in fuel loads across different stages of forest stands, which

directly influence their susceptibility to wildfires. Mature stands were found to have unique fuel characteristics, including a higher accumulation of dried needles and surface debris compared to middle-aged and young stands. These differences in fuel composition and distribution contribute to varying fire behaviors and risks. The fire in the Chir pine forest is often locally ignited by residents to remove debris and encourage grass production (Kumar et al., 2013; Mahmud, 1998). In various forest ecosystems, the forest floor contains a large portion of the biomass present throughout the stand (De Groot et al., 2009). Although the importance of surface fuel is widely acknowledged, its high levels of temporal and geographical variability make it difficult to estimate surface fuel loads accurately (Keane, 2012).

The study found that areas subjected to fuel reduction treatments experienced less burn severity after forest fires, as noted in some short-term studies (Martinson and Omi, 2002). Thinning, pruning, and brush clearing are commonly used fuel reduction methods in Europe and South America (Pivello, 2011). Despite their slow spread and low flames, surface fires can severely damage trees, particularly young saplings and thin-barked species, by consuming leaf litter and woody debris (Laurance, 2003). Fuel plays a crucial role in the spread of forest fires, alongside temperature and ignition potential, which collectively form the three primary elements that drive fire ignition and propagation (Matin et al., 2017). Fuel treatments help reduce wildfire risk by decreasing fuel loads and altering fuel structures, thereby limiting fire intensity and spread (Stephens, 1998). However, the use of prescribed fires in the spring to manage accumulated fuel loads and restore natural fire cycles in western forests has been a topic of debate (Thompson and Purcell, 2016). Additionally, complex interactions exist between surface fuel consumption, climate, and landscape features, with variations in the depth of the remaining organic layer after a fire influencing soil moisture and temperature (Kasischke and Johnstone, 2005). Prolonged fire exclusion in Western regions has increased wildfire risks, particularly in drier forests, as found by Agee and Skinner (2005). They recommended fuel reduction strategies, including reducing surface fuels, increasing crown heights, thinning crown density, and preserving large fire-resistant trees through prescribed burns and thinning. Similarly, Peterson et al., (2013) emphasized the importance of managing fuel accumulation in wildfire-prone ecosystems. Understanding the spatial and temporal variations in forest fuel conditions is critical for assessing overall fire hazard and risk, especially in dry oak-dominated areas (Stambaugh et al., 2011).

This higher frequency is likely due to the greater accumulation of surface fuel and dried needles on the forest floor. Most fires occur during the driest months of the year, particularly in May and July. Notably, in 2019, middle-aged stands experienced the highest number of fires, whereas in 2009, young stands were more affected than both mature and middle-aged stands highlighting the need for targeted fire management strategies tailored to each stand stage to effectively mitigate wildfire hazards. The study concluded that mature stands in the Chir pine forest of Karakar, District Swat, are more prone to fire incidents due to higher surface fuel loads and dried needles. Significant differences in fuel loads across young, middle, and mature stages influence fire susceptibility, underscoring the need for targeted management strategies. Implementing prescribed burns and comprehensive fuel management plans

can effectively reduce wildfire risks and enhance forest resilience. These findings are crucial for developing tailored fire management strategies suited to each forest stand stage. One limitation of this study was its reliance on historical fire data from 2000 to 2022, which was incomplete due to gaps caused by political instability, such as Talibanization in Swat.

The study's focus on a specific geographic area (Karakar, District Swat) may also limit the generalization of its findings to other regions with different ecological and climatic conditions. Additionally, while the study effectively correlates fuel loads with fire incidents, it does not thoroughly explore other influencing factors such as human activities, weather patterns, or insect infestations that could also impact fire behavior. Future studies should address these limitations by including more comprehensive and up-to-date fire records, expanding research into other geographical areas, and examining additional variables such as human influence, climatic variations, and pest infestations to better understand the complexities of fire dynamics in Chir pine forests.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated surface fuel loads and fire events across different forest stand stages in the subtropical Chir pine forest of Karakar, District Swat, using data from 2000 to 2022. Results showed that mature stands experienced more fire incidents due to higher surface fuel loads and dried needles, with fires occurring mainly in May and July. Middle-aged stands recorded more fires in 2019, while younger stands had the highest incidents in 2009. Statistical analysis revealed significant differences in fuel loads and fire susceptibility between young and mature stands, while middle and mature stages showed no significant differences. The findings indicate that fuel loads significantly influence fire susceptibility across forest stand stages, with mature stands having distinct fuel characteristics. These variations highlight the need for targeted forest management strategies, including prescribed burns and fuel reduction, to effectively mitigate wildfire risks. The study emphasizes the importance of a comprehensive fire management plan that considers both the quantity and composition of surface fuels to enhance prevention and suppression efforts in subtropical Chir pine forests.

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AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

Sultan Muhammad conceived and designed and supervised the study. Haseen Ullah executed the experiment, Hamid Ur Rahman analyzed the data. Kaleem Mehmood interpreted the data, critically revised the manuscript for important intellectual contents and approved the final version.

REFERENCES

- Muhammad, S., Ali, A., Mehmood, K., Ahmad, H., Hayat, M., Khan, M.T., Arbab, N., Nizami, M. and Fahad, S. 2024. Temporal variations in burn severity among various vegetation layers in subtropical *Pinus Roxburghii* (Chir Pine) forest of Hindu Kush Mountain range. *Trees, Forests and People*, 18, p.100664.
- Mather, A. 2003. Global Forest Resources Assessment 2000 Main Report-FAO Forestry Paper 140, FAO, Rome, 2001, xxvii+ 479pp, price \$40.00, ISBN 92 5 104642-5, ISSN 0258-6150. *Land Use Policy*, 2(20), 195.
- Luo, L., Tang, Y., Zhong, S., Bian, X., and Heilman, W. E. 2013. Will future climate favor more erratic wildfires in the Western United States? *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, 52(11), 2410-2417.
- HASHMI, M. M., HABIB, M., ABBASI, U. A., and TARIQ, R. S. 2014. Assessment of Carbon Stocks and Biodiversity in Karore Forest, Rawalpindi-North, Pakistan. *European Academic Research*, 2, 7490-7498.
- Negi, M. S., and Kumar, A. 2016. Assessment of increasing threat of forest fires in Uttarakhand, using remote sensing and GIS techniques. *Global Journal of Advanced Research*, 3(6), 457-468.
- Stephens, S. L. 1998. Evaluation of the effects of silvicultural and fuels treatments on potential fire behavior in Sierra Nevada mixed-conifer forests. *Forest ecology and management*, 105(1-3), 21-35.
- Chuvieco, E., Cocero, D., Riano, D., Martin, P., Martinez-Vega, J., De La Riva, J., and Pérez, F. 2004. Combining NDVI and surface temperature for the estimation of live fuel moisture content in forest fire danger rating. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 92(3), 322-331.
- Burgan, R. E., Klaver, R. W., and Klaver, J. M. 1998. Fuel models and fire potential from satellite and surface observations. *International journal of wildland fire*, 8(3), 159-170.
- Kandya, A. K., Kimothi, M. M., Jadhav, R. N., and Agarwal, J. P. 1998. Application of Geographic Information System in Identification of Fire-Prone Areas: A Feasibility Study in Parts of Junagadh (Gujarat). *Indian Forester*, 124(7), 531-536.
- Shvidenko, A., and Goldammer, J. G. 2001. Fire situation in Russia. *International Forest Fire News*, 24, 41-59.
- Iqbal, M. 2003. Deforestation in NWFP. National Institute of Public Administration (NIPA), Karachi, 8(3), pp.26-30.
- Mahmud, N. 1998. Revised Working Plan for Giddarpur Forest of AgrorTanawalForest Division, District Mansehra (Pakistan). 12-15.
- Stephens, S. L., Moghaddas, J. J., Edminster, C., Fiedler, C. E., Haase, S., Harrington, M., and Youngblood, A. 2009. Fire treatment effects on vegetation structure, fuels, and potential fire severity in western US forests. *Ecological Applications*, 19(2), 305-320.
- Keane, R. E. 2012. Describing wildland surface fuel loading for fire management: a review of approaches, methods and systems. *International Journal of Wildland Fire*, 22(1), 51-62.
- Swetnam, T. W. 1993. Fire history and climate change in giant sequoia groves. *Science*, 262(5135), 885-889.
- Reinhardt, E. D., Keane, R. E., Calkin, D. E., and Cohen, J. D. 2008. Objectives and considerations for wildland fuel treatment in forested ecosystems of the interior western United States. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 256(12), 1997-2006.
- Ali, H., Shah, J., Jan, A.K. 2008. Medicinal value of family Ranunculaceae of District Dir Pakistan. *Pak. J. Bot.* 39 (4), 1037 –1044.
- Kumar, M., Sheikh, M. A., Bhat, J. A., and Bussmann, R. W. 2013. Effect of fire on soil nutrients and under story vegetation in Chir pine forest in Garhwal Himalaya, India. *Acta Ecologica Sinica*, 33(1), 59–63.
- De Groot, W. J., Pritchard, J. M., and Lynham, T. J. 2009. Forest floor fuel consumption and carbon emissions in Canadian boreal forest fires. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research*, 39(2), 367-382.
- Martinson, E. J., and Omi, P. N. 2002. Performance of fuel treatments subjected to wildfires. *FIRE, FUEL TREATMENTS, AND ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION*. [vp]. 16-18 Apr.
- Pivello, V. R. 2011. The use of fire in the Cerrado and Amazonian rainforests of Brazil: past and present. *Fire ecology*, 7, 24-39.
- Laurance, W. F. 2003. Slow burn: the insidious effects of surface fires on tropical forests. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, 18(5), 209-212.
- Matin, M. A., Chitale, V. S., Murthy, M. S., Uddin, K., Bajracharya, B., and Pradhan, S. 2017. Understanding forest fire patterns and risk in Nepal using remote sensing, geographic information system and historical fire data. *International journal of wildland fire*, 26(4), 276-286.
- Thompson, C. M., and Purcell, K. L. 2016. Conditions inside fisher dens during prescribed fires; what is the risk posed by spring underburns?. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 359, 156-161.
- Kasischke, E. S., and Johnstone, J. F. 2005. Variation in postfire organic layer thickness in a black spruce forest complex in interior Alaska and its effects on soil temperature and moisture. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research*, 35(9), 2164-2177.

- Agee, J. K., and Skinner, C. N. 2005. Basic principles of forest fuel reduction treatments. *Forest ecology and management*, 211(1-2), 83-96.
- Peterson, S. H., Franklin, J., Roberts, D. A., and van Wagtendonk, J. W. 2013. Mapping fuels in yosemite national park. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research*, 43(1), 7-17.
- Stambaugh, M. C., Dey, D. C., Guyette, R. P., He, H. S., and Marschall, J. M. 2011. Spatial patterning of fuels and fire hazards across a central US deciduous forest region. *Landscape ecology*, 26, 923-935.